

EFFECT OF FOOT REFLEXOLOGY AND BODY MASSAGE ON SELECTED OUTCOMES AMONG NEONATES UNDERGOING PHOTOTHERAPY

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Abstract

Background: Phototherapy is the primary mode of treatment of physiological jaundice but it has many adverse reactions. Foot reflexology and body massage therapy have recognized as novel approaches to neonatal care that improve the management of neonatal illnesses and overall health. **Aim:** To evaluate the effect of foot reflexology and body massage on selected outcomes among neonates undergoing phototherapy. **Methods:** A single-blinded randomized controlled trial design was utilized on a purposive sample of one hundred and five full-term neonates with physiological jaundice from Neonatal Intensive Care Unit at EL Monira Pediatric Hospital that is affiliated to Cairo University from April 2023 to June 2024. The sample randomly assigned to three equal groups, namely foot reflexology, body massage and control using block randomization. **Tools:** two tools were utilized: neonatal characteristics and neonates' clinical outcomes. Foot reflexology and body massage were performed once a day for fifteen minutes for five consecutive days. Transcutaneous bilirubin and serum bilirubin levels, defecation frequency and phototherapy duration were recorded daily through the intervention five days. **Results:** Before intervention there were no significant differences in the mean of transcutaneous and serum bilirubin levels among the three study groups, while it decreased significantly in reflexology and massage groups compared to control after intervention. Defecation frequency increased significantly for all neonates in the three study groups from the second day. Total days mean on phototherapy decreased significantly in reflexology and massage groups compared to control group. **Conclusion:** Neonates undergoing phototherapy who received foot reflexology or body massage had lower bilirubin levels, more defecation frequency and shorter duration on phototherapy than who not receive. Foot reflexology and body massage had the same effect on bilirubin levels, and duration on phototherapy. **Recommendation:** Foot reflexology and body massage must be taken into consideration as a complementary modality that should be incorporated into nursing care because it is a safe, cost-efficient and well tolerated by neonates with physiological jaundice undergoing phototherapy.

Keywords: Foot Reflexology, Body Massage, Neonatal Outcomes, Phototherapy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Neonatal jaundice (NJ) is a prevalent health problem among term and late preterm neonates. Approximately 60% of term and 80% of preterm neonates develop hyperbilirubinemia in the first week of life, and nearly 10% of breastfed neonates still have NJ at one month of age [1]. It is one of the most common reasons for neonatal hospitalization. Bilirubin is one of the breakdown products of haemoglobin [2]. NJ is a

yellowish colouring of the skin and sclera, and is caused by an excess of bilirubin in the blood. When the total serum bilirubin level in neonates is 5 mg/dl, jaundice develops [2]. High levels of serum bilirubin are neurotoxic; therefore, early diagnosis and treatment of NJ are crucial [3]. Currently, several methods are available for treatment of jaundice, however, the main form of treatment involves the use of phototherapy. Phototherapy associated with side effects such as transient skin rashes, mild hyperthermia, and retinal damage. Reducing the duration of phototherapy may diminish its side effects [2].

Today, the use of complementary and alternative medicine therapies in health care systems around the world is being emphasized. Nurses can use these ways along with regular treatments to promote health. In this regard, foot reflexology, which is one of the six most widely used treatments in complementary medicine, is effective not only in the treatment of diseases but also in maintaining health [4]. Reflexology can be defined as the science of stimulating points that relate to the internal organs of the body [5]. Reflexology has existed in Egypt since about 2330 B.C. and in ancient China 4000 years ago [5]. The feet are sensitive to pressure, traction and movement. Different degrees of pressure, such as massage and touch, stimulate the end of the sensory nerves connected to receptors [6]. Using reflexology, by applying compression technique on the reflection point of each organ, the blockage in the energy flow path is eliminated and as a result, the energy movement flows in its channels [6]. [7] reported that foot reflexology prevented neonatal jaundice by increasing bowel movements and reducing the enterohepatic circulation of bilirubin. [8] reported that reflexology has been effective in improving bilirubin level and decrease duration of hospitalization. Neonatal body massage is described as a structured touch of the skin, and in many cultures, it is a tradition that begins immediately after birth. Performing infant body massage differs worldwide concerning duration, intensity, extent, use of oil, and parental involvement. Neonatal body massage has been used in neonatal intensive care units to some benefit for various outcomes such as weight gain, reduced length of stay at hospital and postnatal complications [9]. Neonatal body massage is useful for controlling bilirubin into normal values, neonate care by providing massage on the body can stimulate the vagus nerve and can increase the production of food-absorbing hormones that can increase the secretion of gastric and pancreatic juices and increase the amount of milk sucked by the neonate and improve digestive function in neonates better [10]. [11] indicated that massage therapy had significant effects on total serum bilirubin levels, and defecation frequency in neonates who received phototherapy for indirect hyperbilirubinemia. Massage therapy can be added as a routine care for full-term neonates with hyperbilirubinemia under phototherapy and may be an effective supplementary intervention. Neonatal nurses are key persons in NICU and they have a proactive role in assessment and treatment of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. So that, they should be equipped with the most innovative evidences in neonatal care. To improve the quality of care and preserve the best long-term outcomes for neonates, neonatal nurses should be aware of the most effective complementary and alternative therapies, such as foot reflexology [12]. So far, little research has been done on comparing the effects of foot reflexology and body massage on physiological jaundice. Therefore, this study was

performed to evaluate the effect of foot reflexology and body massage on bilirubin levels, defecation frequency and duration of phototherapy among neonates undergoing phototherapy.

1.2 Operational definition

For the purpose of the current study the following operational definition will be addressed:

Selected outcomes: include the following: transcutaneous bilirubin and serum bilirubin levels, defecation frequency and phototherapy duration days.

2. METHODS

2.1 Aim

To evaluate the effect of foot reflexology and body massage on selected outcomes among neonates undergoing phototherapy. To achieve the aim of the current study the following research hypotheses were postulated:

H1: Neonate's group undergoing phototherapy who are receiving foot reflexology/or/body massage, will have lower bilirubin levels, more defecation frequency and shorter duration of phototherapy than control group.

H2: Neonates' group undergoing phototherapy who are receiving foot reflexology, will have lower bilirubin levels, shorter duration of phototherapy and more defecation frequency than those who are receiving body massage.

2.2 Design

A single-blinded randomized controlled trial (RCT) design was utilized.

2.3 Setting

The study was conducted at the NICU of EL Monira Paediatric Hospital that is affiliated to Cairo University. Capacity of the NICU is about 56 incubators well-equipped to provide care for free to neonates from all over Egypt. This NICU is divided into four sections (two intensive care (IC), an intermediate ICU, and a jaundice section). The current study was conducted in the section of neonatal jaundice, providing care to 10 cases of neonates with neonatal jaundice requiring phototherapy and/or exchange transfusion.

2.4 Participants

A purposive sample of 105 neonates who met the inclusion criteria: full-term neonates \geq 37 weeks of gestation, body weight \geq 2.5 kg, newly diagnosed with physiological jaundice and first-time undergoing conventional phototherapy (Drager phototherapy 4000) included in the study and randomly assigned to equally three groups foot reflexology, body massage and control. Using the blocked randomization.

Participants: a total of 400 neonates were eligible. Of those, 295 were not included in the study because they were not eligible on the basis of the previous inclusion criteria. Of the remaining 105 neonates, 35 neonates were in foot reflexology group, 35 were in body massage group, and 35 were in control group, 11 neonates were dropped out from the study: 4 from foot reflexology group, 2 from body massage group, and 5 from control group the reason for attrition in study groups and control group was early discharge for neonates before completion of 5 days.

2.5 Data Collection Tools

Two tools were developed by the researchers after extensive review of related literature: the following: Neonatal characteristics and medical history sheet, and outcomes recording sheet which include transcutaneous bilirubin level, serum bilirubin level, defecation frequency and phototherapy duration days for five consecutive days.

Procedure

The study was carried out in three phases: the preparatory, the implementation, and the evaluation phase.

Preparatory phase: Official permission was obtained from the director of NICU administrator of the study setting. The researcher introduced herself and explained the procedure to the parents of neonates as well as the benefits of the study. Written informed consent was obtained from each parent after a complete description of the purpose, nature, and benefits of the study.

Recruitment and Randomization of Sample:

The researchers started the enrolment process by assessing newly diagnosed neonates with physiological jaundice undergoing phototherapy at EL Monira (NICU) Paediatric Hospital of Cairo University for eligibility criteria of the trial. After that, a list of neonates who met the criteria was done by the researchers. Thereafter, neonates were randomly allocated into study groups or control group by using blocks to determine to which group

the neonate was assigned. This technique was utilized to maintain allocation concealment to decrease bias and ensure homogeneity between the groups. Sample were allocated in 18 blocks, every block contained six neonates except the last block contain three neonates to complete sample size 105 and every neonate allocated randomly according to the sequence of each block till the block number was ended we start another block till complete the sample size.

Implementation phase: Data collection was done for five consecutive days.

The researcher measured daily transcutaneous bilirubin levels using the Drager Jaundice Meter (JM-105) scale after turning off the phototherapy (for 5 minutes) from the forehead then recorded it in tool II, recorded serum bilirubin from the neonatal medical record, and count daily defecation frequency from nursing sheet and recorded it in tool II for all three groups.

Foot reflexology: The researchers turned off the phototherapy for 5 minutes before the intervention, then the researchers put a neonate in a supine position and completely relaxed (calm and asleep), then held the left foot of the neonate with left hand and gently massaged, then held the right foot and massaged gently, especially the area of the liver for 10 to 15 minutes with the thumb of right hand for two feet. The foot reflexology was performed once a day for 10 to 15 minutes for five consecutive days, one drop of zinc olive cream was used to facilitate foot massage.

Body massage: The researcher turned off the phototherapy for 5 minutes before the intervention, then the researcher put one drop of zinc olive cream in her hands to facilitate massage of neonate and decrease the friction of the skin after that the researcher started the massage on the leg and foot (with one hand used to fix the foot), start with fingers of left leg from up to down each finger from the big toe to the pink toe, massage soul of feet with circular movement, then raise the left leg slightly and massage from up to down with circular movement till reach to inguinal area, repeat these steps in the right leg, then the area around the umbilicus was massaged in a circular motion, the chest was massaged with both two hands, neonate's hands were massaged from fingers to arms toward axillary as (start with left arm with thumb finger to little one and the palm massaged with circular motion then then raise the left arm and massaged from up to down with circular movement till reach to axilla. The face, cheeks, and lips were also gently massaged with the index finger of the researcher, after that put the neonate in prone position with head on one side then the researcher massaged the back of the leg with circular movement and back was massaged. It was performed for 15 minutes per session after one hour between feeding once per day for five consecutive days.

Control group: They received routine hospital care without receiving any interventions. Bilirubin levels (serum bilirubin and transcutaneous bilirubin) were recorded and measured daily for five consecutive days, defecation frequency was counted and phototherapy duration days were recording in tool II for intervention groups.

Evaluation phase: Transcutaneous bilirubin, serum bilirubin levels were measured and recorded, defecation frequency was counted daily for each neonate in the three groups and phototherapy duration was recorded for five consecutive days in tools II.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

A Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) program version 21 was used. The collected data was tabulated, and summarized. Data was computerized and analysed using appropriate descriptive statistics were utilized such as frequencies, mean and standard deviation. Inferential statistical tests to test the research hypotheses as the significance in standard statistical books included Student t-test and chi-square, (ANOVA) test, Level of significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

Fig 1: Distribution for Gender among Three Groups

Fig 2: Frequency Distribution for Mode of Delivery among Three Groups

Table (1): Mean of neonatal characteristics among study groups

Neonate characteristics	Reflexology	Massage	Control	P	Total
	Mean \pm SD				
GA/ wks.	38.17 \pm 1.07	38.34 \pm 1.02	37.94 \pm .96	.26	38.15 \pm 1.02
Age / day	5.40 \pm .94	6.29 \pm 1.07	5.63 \pm 1.45	.06	5.77 \pm 1.15
Onset of jaundice	2.43 \pm .55	2.49 \pm .61	2.57 \pm .65	.61	2.49 \pm .60
Birth weight/ gm	2.96 \pm .33	2.98 \pm .32	2.89 \pm .26	.43	2.94 \pm .30
Weight (on admission)/ gm	2.86 \pm .31	2.84 \pm .28	2.77 \pm .24	.39	2.82 \pm .28

Note: GA= Gestational age wks.= week

Figure (1 and 2) and table (1) indicates that, there were no statistical significant differences among the study groups before intervention regarding their gender, and mode of delivery P = (.63, .12) respectively. Also., no statistical significant differences among study groups in relation to their mean of gestational age per week, age in days, onset of jaundice after birth, birth weight and weight before intervention, P = (.26, .06, .61, .39) respectively.

Table (2): Comparison of transcutaneous bilirubin level mean among study groups over the study period

Transcutaneous bilirubin level over the study period	Groups			
	Reflexology	Massage	Control	P value
	Mean			
On admission	18.45 \pm 2.73	18.57 \pm 2.83	19.10 \pm 2.84	.59
1 st	16.23	17.38	17.62	.11
2 nd	13.24	13.78	14.75	.11
3 rd	10.38	11.08	14.74	.04
4 th	7.32	8.41	9.83	.04
5 th	6.03	6.06	7.71	.00

Table (2) reveals that there were no statistical significant differences among foot reflexology, body massage and control groups before intervention regarding their mean of transcutaneous bilirubin (18.45 \pm 2.73, 18.57 \pm 2.83 & 19.10 \pm 2.84) respectively, p = (.59). While it is decreased significantly in foot reflexology and body massage groups compared to control at 3rd, 4th and 5th day after intervention P= (.04, .04, & .00) respectively.

Table (3): Comparison of total serum bilirubin level mean among study groups over the study period

Total Serum bilirubin Level over the study period	Groups			
	Reflexology	Massage	Control	P
	Mean			
On admission	18.72 \pm 2.47	18.47 \pm 2.80	19.89 \pm 2.94	.07
1 st	16.89	17.56	17.95	.28
2 nd	13.76	14.37	15.63	.02
3 rd	10.88	11.53	13.41	.00
4 th	8.46	9.10	10.85	.00
5 th	6.75	6.72	8.64	.00

Table (3) demonstrates that there were no statistical significant differences among foot reflexology, body massage and control groups before intervention regarding their mean of total serum bilirubin level (18.72 ± 2.47 , 18.47 ± 2.80 & 19.89 ± 2.94) respectively, $p = (.075)$, while it is decreased significantly in foot reflexology and body massage groups compared to control at 2nd, 3rd, 4th, & 5th days $P = (.02, .00, .00, \& .00)$ respectively.

Table (4): Comparison of daily defecation frequency mean among the study groups over the study

Defecation frequency over the study period	Groups			P
	Control	Massage	Reflexology	
	Mean \pm SD			
1 st	1.90 ± 0.68	1.85 ± 0.57	1.90 ± 0.64	.16
2 nd	2.25 ± 0.79	3.40 ± 0.75	3.10 ± 0.89	.02
3 rd	2.90 ± 1.12	4.00 ± 1.17	3.20 ± 1.00	.02
4 th	3.50 ± 0.87	4.30 ± 0.80	3.90 ± 0.81	.00
5 th	3.50 ± 0.87	4.50 ± 0.72	4.00 ± 0.81	.00

Table (4) no significant differences among the three study groups regarding to their defecation frequency mean before intervention $p = (.16)$. However, the daily defecation frequency increased significantly for all neonates in the three study groups on the second, third, fourth and fifth days after intervention $P = (0.02, .02, .00 \& .00)$ respectively.

Table (5): Comparison of total days on phototherapy mean of the study groups over the study period

Total days on phototherapy	Groups			P
	Reflexology	Massage	Control	
	Mean \pm SD			
	$3.83 \pm .70$	$3.89 \pm .83$	$4.51 \pm .65$.00
	$3.83 \pm .70$	$3.89 \pm .83$.75

Table (5) demonstrates that the mean total days on phototherapy is decreased significantly in foot reflexology and body massage groups compared to control $P = (.00)$, the same table demonstrates that no statistical significant differences between foot reflexology and body massage groups in their total days on phototherapy $P = (.75)$.

4. DISCUSSION

The current study findings revealed that foot reflexology and body massage are more effective in reducing neonatal transcutaneous bilirubin level compared to control group at third, fourth and fifth days after intervention. These finding are supported with [13] who studied "Comparing the effect of foot reflexology and massage therapy on serum bilirubin levels in neonates with hyperbilirubinemia treated with phototherapy: a randomized clinical trial" and revealed that it seems that foot reflexology and massage are more effective in reducing neonatal transcutaneous bilirubin level compared to control group. In the same line with [8] who studied "Effects of foot reflexology on neonatal jaundice: A randomized sham-controlled trial" and reported that neonates in the foot reflexology group had significantly lower cutaneous bilirubin levels than those of the sham control groups

on the first and third days after the intervention. Also, [14] who studied "Effects of body massage on response to phototherapy in neonatal hyperbilirubinemia: a randomized clinical trial" and reported that massage is more effective in the early hours of phototherapy when skin bilirubin levels are higher compared with the control group.

The current results were contradicted with [15] who studied "Effects of Massage on Duration of Phototherapy in Premature Infants Admitted to a Neonatal Intensive Care Unit" and showed a non-significant difference in the level of transcutaneous bilirubin between the massage and control groups.

Regarding the total serum bilirubin level (TSB), the current findings revealed that on the second, third, fourth, and fifth days after foot reflexology and body massage interventions the bilirubin level decreased significantly compared to the control group. Although the current findings noted that there were no significant differences between the foot reflexology and body massage groups in terms of the level of TB, its decreasing trend was faster in the reflexology group than the massage group. The current findings are in accordance with [16] who studied " Comparison of the effect of foot reflexology and body massage on physiological indicators and bilirubin levels in neonates under phototherapy" and found that the bilirubin level decreased significantly after reflexology and massage interventions compared to the control group. Also, the current findings were parallel with the findings of [7] who investigated " Effect of foot reflexology on neonates' clinical outcomes with hyperbilirubinemia undergoing phototherapy: A randomized controlled trial" and illustrated that the bilirubin levels of neonates in the reflexology group were significantly lower than those in the control group. From the researchers' point of view, this may be resulting from foot reflexology mechanism can reduce serum bilirubin level by increasing the vagal activity, which by turn increases the gastric motility and stool frequency. The resulting decrease in enterohepatic circulation will promote the excretion of bilirubin.

The study results are in accordance with [17] who studied " Effect of field massage on bilirubin level and stool passage frequency among neonates with hyperbilirubinemia under phototherapy" and revealed that, from the 2nd to 6th days was lower among the study group than control group with statistical significant difference.

The current study findings demonstrated that foot reflexology and body massage groups had a higher mean defecation frequency than the control group, with statistically significant differences from the second day throughout the five consecutive days of intervention. This in the same line with [8] and revealed that the study group had a higher mean stool frequency than the control group, with statistical significant differences throughout the study. As well as the current study findings are in accordance with [18] about "Comparison of the effectiveness of bath and massage in bilirubin levels in neonates" and reported that the experimental group had a more frequent defecation daily than the control group. The current study results are contradicted with [19] who studied "Effects of neonatal massage on jaundiced neonates undergoing phototherapy" and reported that defecation frequency increased by time in control and massage groups. From the researchers' point of view, this may be related to massage, increased motility,

resulting in more defecation and allowing meconium to be excreted faster, thus causing bilirubin to be excreted with feces and reducing the reabsorption of bilirubin into the blood circulation. In addition, neonatal massage increases blood circulation, lymph, and tissue fluid circulation.

Concerning phototherapy duration, the current study findings illustrated that the mean total days on phototherapy for control group is increased significantly compared to foot reflexology and body massage groups 4.5, 3.8, 3.8 respectively, while there was no significance between foot reflexology and body massage groups, this is in the same line with [19] who found that the span of hospitalization declined from 94.8 to 81 hours (3.9 to 3.3 days) and the term of phototherapy decreased from 84 to 74 hours (3.5 to 3 days)in the back rub field gathering.

Also., [20] who investigated " Yakson's Massage Versus Kangaroo Mother Care on Phototherapy Duration and Serum Bilirubin Level among Neonates with Hyperbilirubinemia" and found that there were highly statistical significance differences between the two interventions groups and control group regarding to the duration phototherapy and the duration of hospital stay. In another hand [21] who studied "Comparing the effect of kangaroo mother care and field massage on serum bilirubin level of term neonates with hyperbilirubinemia under phototherapy in the neonatal ward" and found that the mean duration of phototherapy and hospitalization had no significant difference between two intervention groups and significantly higher in control group compared to intervention groups

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Neonates undergoing phototherapy who received foot reflexology or body massage had lower bilirubin levels, more defecation frequency and shorter duration on phototherapy than who not receive. Foot reflexology and body massage had the same effect on bilirubin levels, and duration on phototherapy. **Recommendation:** Foot reflexology and body massage must be taken into consideration as a complementary modality that should be incorporated into nursing care because it is a safe, cost-efficient and well tolerated by neonates with physiological jaundice undergoing phototherapy.

6. Limitations

There were not limitations in the current study.

7. Abbreviations

NJ	Neonatal Jaundice.
RCT	Randomized Control Trial.
LED	Light Emitting Diodes.
NICU	Neonatal Intensive Care Unit.
TSB	Total Serum Bilirubin.
JM	Jaundice Meter
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science.

8. Declarations

8.1 Ethical Considerations

This study was part of a Doctorate thesis; a primary approval was attained from the research ethical committee in the Faculty of Nursing, Cairo University. All full-term neonates' parents who participated in the study were informed about the aim, procedure, benefits, and nature of the study and the written consent was obtained by the researchers from parents. The researchers emphasized that participation in the study was voluntary, and parents can refuse to participate in the study without any reason and obtained data was only used for the research purpose. The confidentiality of information was assured and the parents had the right to withdraw from the study at any time during the study without any effect on the care provided to their neonates.

8.2 Availability of data and materials

The data that support the findings of this trial are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

8.3 Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

8.4 Funding

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References

- 1) Hockenberry, M. J., Wilson, D., & Rodgers, C. C. (2021). *Wong's essentials of pediatric nursing-e-book* (11th ed.). Elsevier Health Sciences. ISBN 9780323749657.
- 2) Watchko, J. F. (2025). Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. *Klaus and Fanaroff's Care of the High-Risk Neonate-E-BOOK*, 220. Elsevier. doi: 10.1016/j.clinthera.2023.05.012.
- 3) Fanaroff, A. A., & Fanaroff, J. M. (Eds.). (2025). *Klaus and Fanaroff's Care of the High-Risk Neonate-E-BOOK*. Elsevier Health Sciences.
- 4) Ng, J. Y., Dhawan, T., Dogadova, E., Taghi-Zada, Z., Vacca, A., Wieland, L. S., & Moher, D. (2022). Operational definition of complementary, alternative, and integrative medicine derived from a systematic search. *BMC complementary medicine and therapies*, 22(1), 104. doi.org/10.1186/s12906-022-03556-7.
- 5) Hull, R. (2023). *The complete guide to reflexology*. Healing Arts Press. 11th ed, pp (110-119) ISBN: 9781644116258.
- 6) Whatley, J., Perkins, J., & Samuel, C. (2022). Reflexology: Exploring the mechanism of action. *Complementary Therapies in Clinical Practice*, 48, 101606.
- 7) Badr, E. A., & Ibrahim, H. (2023). Effect of foot reflexology on neonates' clinical outcomes with hyperbilirubinemia undergoing phototherapy: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Neonatal Nursing*, 29(2), 361-367. DOI:10.1016/j.jnn.2022.07.023.

- 8) Moghadam, M. B., Esmaeili, M., Khosravan, S., & Mojtavavi, S. J. (2020). Effects of foot reflexology on neonatal jaundice: A randomized sham-controlled trial. *European Journal of Integrative Medicine*, 38, 101173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eujim.2020.101173>.
- 9) Mrljak R, Arnsteg Danielsson A, Hedov G, Garmy P. Effects of Infant Massage: A Systematic Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022 May 24;19(11):6378. doi: 10.3390/ijerph19116378. PMID: 35681968; PMCID: PMC9179989.
- 10) Sari, H. E., & Yulianti, N. T. (2023). Effectiveness of massage therapy for the treatment of neonatal jaundice: a systematic review and meta-analysis. DOI: 10.26911/FP.ICPH.09.2022.29
- 11) Korkmaz, G., & Esenay, F. I. (2020). Effects of massage therapy on indirect hyperbilirubinemia in newborns who receive phototherapy. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 49 (1) , 91 - 100 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2019.11.004>.
- 12) Mahdy, N. M., El Kreem, H. E. A., Mohamed, N. T., & Aziz, S. M. A. (2023). Effect of Foot Reflexology on Physiological Index for Neonates with Hyperbilirubinemia at Neonatal Intensive Care Unit. *Assiut Scientific Nursing Journal*, 11(40), 240-249. DOI: 10.21608/asnj.2024.249869.1716.
- 13) Nikzad, N., Kazemi, M., & Abdoli, F. (2021). Comparing the effect of foot reflexology and massage therapy on serum bilirubin levels in neonates with hyperbilirubinemia treated with phototherapy: a randomized clinical trial. *Journal of Mazandaran University of Medical Sciences*, 31 (200), 61 - 72. Clinical Trials Registry Number: IRCT20180206038642N3. URL: <http://jmums.mazums.ac.ir/article-1-16205-en.html>.
- 14) Boskabadi, H., Alfi, N., Abrishami, M., Moradi, A., Kiani, M. A., & Zakerihamidi, M. (2020). Effects of body massage on response to phototherapy in neonatal hyperbilirubinemia: a randomized clinical trial. *International Journal of Pediatrics*, 8(5), 11347-11353. DOI: 10.22038/ijp.2020.41101.3462.
- 15) Karbandi, S., Boskabadi, H., & Kalatemolae, M. (2020). Effects of Massage on Duration of Phototherapy in Premature Infants Admitted to a Neonatal Intensive Care Unit. *Journal of Babol University of Medical Sciences*, 18(1), 11-17. doi:10.22038/ebcj.2015.6057
- 16) Jazayeri, Z., Sajadi, M., Dalvand, H., & Zolfaghari, M. (2021). Comparison of the effect of foot reflexology and body massage on physiological indicators and bilirubin levels in neonates under phototherapy. *Complementary Therapies in Medicine*, 59, 102684. doi: 10.1016/j.ctim.2021.102684. Epub 2021 Feb 17.
- 17) Abdelhamid Zaki, N. (2019). Effect of field massage on bilirubin level and stool passage frequency among neonates with hyperbilirubinemia under phototherapy. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*, 10(2), 45-55. DOI: 10.21608/ejhc.2019.33509.
- 18) Dehghani K, Nouroozi E, Mandegari Z, Salmani N, Shakiba M. Comparison of the effectiveness of bath and massage in bilirubin levels in neonates. *Iran J Neonatol*. 2020;10(3): 45-50. doi:10.22038/ijn.2019.33607.1484.
- 19) Dabour, S. A., Assar, E. H., Ismail, Y. M., & Afify, M. A. (2020). Effects of neonatal massage on jaundiced neonates undergoing phototherapy. *Benha Journal of Applied Sciences*, 5(4 part (2)), 247-251. DOI: 10.21608/bjas.2020.136343.
- 20) Ahmed Mahmoud, H., Amin Elzehri, M., & Abdallah Mohammed, H. (2020). Yakson's Massage Versus Kangaroo Mother Care on Phototherapy Duration and Serum Bilirubin Level among Neonates with Hyperbilirubinemia. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*, 11(2), 1147-1162. Doi: 10.21608/EJHC.2020.269230.
- 21) Iori Kenari, R., Aziznejadrosan, P., Mojaveri, M. H., & Hajian-Tilaki, K. (2020). Comparing the effect of kangaroo mother care and field massage on serum bilirubin level of term neonates with hyperbilirubinemia under phototherapy in the neonatal ward. *Caspian journal of internal medicine*, 11(1), 34. DOI: 10.22088/cjim.11.1.34.